

PLANNING, SELECTION AND DEVELOPMENT OF HUMAN RESOURCES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

F.R.Valiyeva

Associate Professor of the Institute of International School of Finance
Technology and Science (PhD)

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ANNOTATION

In the period of modernization and diversification of the economy of Uzbekistan, increasing the income of citizens, standard of living and the volume of GDP produced in the republic, as a result, strengthening the independence of our country, creating new jobs to ensure the employment of the population in order to improve the well-being of our people, improving working conditions and increasing the intellectual potential of labor resources are also the tasks of today. is one of the most important issues.

Key words: quantity, quality, current personnel, flexibility, implemented policy, individual characteristic;

At the present time, in order to ensure the stable and rapid development of the republic's economy, comprehensive, rationally based priority tasks and directions, social and educational development plans and programs are being developed for our future.

The new market relations that are being formed in our country, which are being strengthened in many aspects, serve to increase the number and potential of educated, talented, enterprising highly qualified personnel who actively and honestly serve in order to increase the weight of the intelligentsia of the population, the strength of the economy of our republic and the welfare of the population. has an impact on the activities of higher education organizations.

criteria are used in the analysis of personnel policy :

- quantity and quality of personnel;
- lack of current personnel;
- the flexibility of the implemented policy;
- taking into account the interests of the employee.

Professional skills of the manager play a major role in the effective management of human resources, and these illustrated in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Management skills of the manager.

In the management of human resources, it is necessary to take into account the individual characteristics (character) of personnel and its management processes. Knowing the individual characteristics of the personnel allows the manager to correctly approach a specific person with the requirements of this or that activity, to choose the right forms and methods of treatment, and to organize the team. The following characters of individuals differ from each other: *sanguine, phlegmatic, choleric, melancholic*.

Sanguine: quickly gets out with people and actively communicates with them, does not like monotonous work and easily changes one type of activity to another, cheerful, easily controls his emotions and quickly adapts to new conditions. Speaks loudly, quickly and in chunks, adds expressive behavior and gestures to his speech . He is not indifferent to his mental abilities.

Phlegmatic: his behavior is even and unweighted, he is alien to making hasty decisions, he is slow to move from one activity to another, he adapts to new conditions for a long time and is less frustrated. It takes a strong external push to get him to do something. Endurance and self-discipline are unique. He speaks calmly and does not show his emotions sharply .

Choleric: he is distinguished by his extreme diligence, he is very active and does not know where to put his energy; can work "with no head up" and overcome difficulties with a high spirit. Often, after increased activity, a period of depression begins and exhaustion occurs, especially when the active action does not bring success. Choleric has an unstable mood (even small things can affect him), he is curious, self-centered and one-sided. He speaks quickly.

Melancholic: overly impressionable, quick to get carried away, and cares about trivial things; in difficult situations, he often falls into a state of confusion, the mood of oppression and boredom is characteristic of him; deeply saddened by failure. He absorbs changes in life slowly and is very slow to get used to them; is shy, nervous, and usually reacts anxiously to indecisive jokes.

Table 1. General features of human nature .

Personality type	Aspects of human nature	
	Positive	Negative

Civic responsibility and attitude to duty	<i>Self - love, good conscience, persistence, thrift, etc</i>	<i>Indolence, indifference, extravagance, etc</i>
Attitude towards people	<i>Cannibalism, kindness, benevolence, etc</i>	<i>F imprudence, inner space and other events</i>
Self-attitude	<i>Modesty, modesty, orderliness</i>	<i>Kalondimo glik, boasting, boasting</i>

Organizational culture is the psychological nature (climate) and value system in the organization, which shapes the employee environment and gives it a special touch. Organizational culture has a positive or negative impact on performance. Western scientists distinguish 10 categories of organizational culture:

- It is the recognition of the individuality of a person ;
- Information exchange and collaboration;
- Appearance and dress;
- of the human daughter ;
- to understand and accept changes ;
- Gender differences and attitudes;
- System of needs and priorities;
- one's own faith and the faith of others ;
- Knowledge and personal habits of the specialty b ;
- Mode of operation and uniqueness.

Factors affecting organizational culture.

When analyzing the factors affecting organizational culture , it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that the individual behavior of individuals working in a group is very complex and diverse. These factors are interdependent .

1. Morals are relatively general beliefs about what is right and what is wrong. In this the general tendency of people emerges.

2 . Attitudes are a process of manifesting different ways of creating values . In this, mutual relations and influence of individuals and groups occur .

3. Behavior is a variety of human behavior are forms. People show their culture according to the requirements of this or that situation .

As factors affecting the leadership activity, it is possible to list the working hours of the leader and the creation of a work plan related to his activities . The activity of the leader is organized on the basis of the system of plans. The system consists of plans in the house :

1. Strategic plan;
2. Annual plan;
3. Quarter plan;
4. Monthly plan;
5. Weekly plan;
6. Day plan.

Each of these plans is created in the sequence listed. This is natural , because each subsequent plan is elaborated based on the goals, issues, and arguments of the previous plan. Together, these six plans will slowly and steadily advance towards the leader's desired future . Under the influence of the system of plans, time is always spent in each period of the leader's

life to cultivate only distant and holy intentions . The logic of the planning system is that the leader achieves the strategic goal through daily plans . Daily plans represent the last and most important step in the planning system.

before the previous day . It is based on a weekly plan. In it , the manager lists the tasks that need to be done during the working day tomorrow and the problems that need to be solved . The leader also includes issues that arose yesterday that were not included in the weekly plan into the next day's plan .

When going home in the evening and coming to work in the morning, the issues that have been set in the leader's mind are involuntarily clarified and rational decisions are found . Since the problems in the work process are clearly defined and the ways to solve them are in front of you , the new day is not difficult and unpleasant . On the contrary, a new day is close to the leader's heart . Tasks are easily organized and controlled with enthusiasm. No one gets distracted by unnecessary things.

tasks performed by management during the day can be divided into three types of work. These are: type A, type V and type C jobs. Each work type (A, V, S) is identified by the following two symbols :

How much time should the leader spend to complete this work ?

How much will the organization benefit from the performance of this work by the leader?

A, V, and C types of work of the new day, taking into account their characteristics . Organizing the working day in this way creates the following benefits for the manager :

1. The next day is organized wisely;
2. Things start on a good note;
3. The issues of the day are imagined;
4. All work is divided into important and unimportant tasks;
5. Nervous attacks and nervous breakdowns are rare;
6. The leader's personal results and business horizons will increase. Leaders spend 75% of their working day with different people is spent on mulo qot . All leaders usually use one of two policies in their work :

- "open door " policy;

- "e shi gi yopi q " policy.

employees in the organization (the limit is 20 employees), managers follow one of these policies. The leader should fully entrust his secretary with calling the employees to the leader, organizing reception of them and other visitors from abroad . The invited specialist must be accepted by the leader at the time appointed by him . For a business interview and negotiation to be effective, the leader should choose the meeting place wisely.

All visitors from outside must make an appointment with the manager by phone in advance. Employees working within the organization can easily solve many of their problems over the phone. Visiting the manager's room takes a lot of time from the employees. A leader must be thoroughly prepared for every meeting and negotiation. For this, the leader should thoroughly study the problem in advance ,determine the goal for himself , familiarize himself with all the necessary documents in detail, and make a meeting plan for himself .

Closed-door policymakers can benefit their organizations if they take the following three steps:

To appoint a time when all employees will receive the manager himself regarding the most important issues for the organization, which cannot be delayed (for example, at the beginning of the day _half an hour);

Make a list of some of the most important tasks that the leader personally takes on during the day ;

Assign a list of some of the most important employees that the leader personally takes on during the day .

If the leader goes around his organization at the same time every day, visits all departments and rooms and meets with employees, gets acquainted with their activities, then the number of employees visiting the leader's room will decrease. Usually, as much time as possible is spent on the interview. Not all visitors can express their purpose and problem in a short and clear way. Therefore, the leader should save his time spent on the meeting during the reception. Must know how to finish the meeting on time and get rid of the visitor quickly

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